

Challenges to Women Higher Education in Thiruvallur District, Tamil Nadu

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An educated woman may easily handle her family, make each family member responsible, infuse good qualities in children, participate in the social works and all would lead her towards the socially and economically healthy nation. They have rights to get proper education to perform better in all areas of life. Women education helps them to be more independent and empowered in their life. Education helps them to grow their mind and status and not be a burden to their parents like past times. Education help them to be well aware of their duties and rights as well as realize their responsibilities to contribute towards development of the country as same as men do. Promoting women education and ensuring female literacy have been the major factors behind India’s success.¹

Objectives

- To find out challenges in women higher education in Thiruvallur District, Tamil Nadu
- To explore Governments interest and responsibility in women higher education
- To realise the remedy to increase the women higher education

Sources

Primary and secondary data collected from 40 respondent in the following manner that professors - 5, college female students - 10, college dropout female students - 5, college unjoin student -5, villager from the district -10, and social servicerto women empowerment - 5 by oral interview, District Statistical Hand Book For The Year 2017 – 18, District Census Handbook Thiruvallur, Census Of India 2011, Thiruvallur District Human Development Report 2017 and articles published in online journals, related to the study.

Thiruvallur

The present study was conductedatThiruvallur DistrictinTamil Nadu Stateof India. Thiruvallur district came into being with effect from 1.1.1997. It is having a great historical background as it was

hitherto a part of the erstwhile Chengalpattu district. It is surrounded by Kancheepuram district in the South, Vellore district in the West, Chennai in the East and Andhra Pradesh State in the North.

The district comprises of with 825 Villages, which form 12 Taluks belonging to 4 Revenue Divisions. The Villages are grouped into 14 Development Blocks for the purpose of Rural Development. The Urban population is governed by 5 Municipalities and 10 Town Panchayats. The population of this district is 3728104 persons with 50.32% of Males and 49.68% of Females.² Thiruvallur district ranked the 3rd highest population size in Tamil Nadu The literacy rate is 84.03% as per 2011 Census. The district has recorded higher literacy rate (84%) as compared with the State literacy rate of 80.1%.³

Higher education in Thiruvallur

Higher Education is the shared responsibility of both the Centre and the States. The coordination and determination of standards in institutions is the constitutional obligation of the Central Government. The Central Government provides grants to UGC and establishes Universities in the country.⁴ The Department of Higher Education, MHRD, is responsible for the overall development of the basic infrastructure of Higher Education sector, both in terms of policy and planning. Under a planned development process, the Department looks after expansion of access and qualitative improvement in the Higher Education, through world class Universities, Colleges and other Institutions.⁵ Tamil Nadu state council for higher education was established for the promotion and coordination of higher education at the state level and coordination of the state level programmes with those of the university grants commission.⁶

Thiruvallur have a location advantage as they are close to Chennai harboring higher educational institutions for all key streams. There are remarkable numbers of educational institutions within the district as well. There are seven universities including one veterinary university increasing the opportunities for higher education and human resources development. Nearly 2.5 lakh students were seeking higher education in 23 arts and science colleges, 43 engineering colleges, 21 polytechnic colleges and one medical college and other facilities to study pharmacy, nursing, physiotherapy dental, polytechnic engineering and hotel management.⁷

The department of higher education has been effectively implementing various schemes to encourages aspiring women to pursue higher studies following are some significant schemes provided by the central and state government

- All India Council for Technical Education Scholarships.
- All India Service Examinations like IAS, IPS, IRS, etc.
- Assistance to Lawyers for Starting Their Practice.
- Biotechnology fellowships for doctoral and postdoctoral studies by DBT.
- Book Bank Books Will be Purchased for Medical/ Engineering/ Law / M.B.A./Veterinary / Agri. and Polytechnic / Courses and Placed in the Library.
- Central government Higher Education Special Scholarship for sc, st.
- Department of Science and Technology grants and fellowships.
- Directorate of Non Formal And Adult Education Continuing Education Programme.
- DST's Scholarship Scheme for Women Scientists and Technologists.
- Exemption of Special Fees and Examination Fees to the Post Graduate Girl Students.
- Exemption of Special Fees and Examination Fees to the Under Graduate Students.
- Free Bus Pass Scheme for Students.
- Free Education Granting of Admission fees, Registration fees to ADs / Tribals / AD Converted to Christianity Girls Students Who Join Degree, Post Graduate Degree, and Professional Courses.

- Free education scholarship for Professional Courses (Engineering, Medical, Agriculture, Veterinary, three year Diploma and Law) : BC, MBC & Minorities Welfare Department.
- Free Education Special Fee and Examination Fee to Students Studying in B.A., B.Sc., B.Com., Other Degree Courses and Girl Students of P.G. Courses Special Fee and Examination Fee to Students Study.
- Grant of States Overseas Scholarship to AD/Tribal Students Pursuing Higher Studies in Abroad.
- Higher Education Special Scholarship Scheme.
- Hostels Free Boarding and Lodging to Student.
- Issue of Tools and Appliances Sewing Machines/Carpentry Things to The ITI Holders.
- Junior Research Fellowships for biomedical sciences.
- Maintenance Charges Hostellers and day scholar.
- National Scholarships.
- Post-Doctoral Research Fellow (Scheme).
- Post-matric Scholarships for SC /ST students.
- Reservation and Quota for women.
- Scheme of Apprenticeship Training.
- Scholarship Schemes for ST Students by Ministry of Tribal Affairs.
- Scholarships for Minority Students.
- Special Incentive Scheme For Encouraging Girls Education.
- Special Incentives to Girl Students.
- Special Prize Money Award Grant of One Time Award to The Graduates and Post Graduate and Professional Courses.
- Unemployed Youth Employment Generation Programme (UYEGP), etc.,⁸
Both central and state governments are played vital role to increase women enrolment in higher education in Thiruvallur District.

Challenges to Women Higher Education in Thiruvallur District

In this district, by the people awareness and roll of government, the school education literacy rate is very well but comparing with school education, higher education is not cross the average of total of both, more than fifty present girls student not reach the higher education Comparing to the school level education women's higher education is very low, following are some factors affecting the women higher education

1. Lack of government institutions and colleges

There are only two government arts and Science College located at Ponneri, and Thrutani and no government's professional institution. It is not sufficient to cater educational needs of the women in the district.

2. Education cost, Fees in private sector

Many of the Self-financed and Private Institutes, including medical and engineering colleges, operate on the lines of business ventures. Most of the studying student are settled and out of the district.

3. Education system

Lack of quality of education impacts the transition to higher education. It is causes of fail to attend the entrance exam of higher education like NEET, GATE, CMAT, JEE, etc.,

4. Transport

Educational institutes in the district are concentrated nearer to Chennai, around Poonamallee, on the Chennai Bangalore highway and there are none in many other blocks. People from interior villages have comparatively limited access to educational institutions. There is a need for improvement in infrastructure in terms of road and transport, for better access to the schools as well as higher educational institutes.

5. Job opportunities (Assistance level)

The District has several industrial developments this Small industries and shopping's halls access to get appropriate jobs for the students in school level education. It among women to cater to the industry demand on one hand and opening opportunities for labour on the other hand is the need of the day.

6. During the Period of Maternity and Childcare

Marriage is accepted by people of this district but the period of maternity and child caring is one of the ways to dropout to women in higher education to get degree, women are saying to go and constitute after this period.

7. Illiterate Parent and them Daughter

Illiterate parent not known about the higher education and its process, so they could not able to plan and act properly for daughter's higher education.

8. Other Challenges

These are some individual and social barrier to women higher education that Inferiority complex, shyness, fairness, and wilful adamant about the exams, Inability and fail on the school level exam; Neglect, ignorance, Independency, Conservation Mentality, Domestic Duty, lower socio economic status of parents, Forced to follow orders of elders in family whether at home of parents or parents-in-law, Allowed to get only limited education, love and affection and etc., are barrier of women education

9. Semi challenges

Marriage, co-education, studying at hostels, out of district or other state, etc., not affected the women higher education and accepted by the people but may be consider as semi barrier because these are effect barrier of sometime. It works in the past not now.

Impacts

The above said challenges are obstructs and barrier to the following that to women empowerment, to get high level opportunity in society, to reduce education discrimination within male and female, literacy rate of women higher education, and it affected women quality, skill, and knowledge and activeness on society in this district.

Suggestions

Government must increase the count of colleges and institutions, fix low level education cast and fees, build basic infrastructure and transport to reach the institutions easy, take to special coaching to attend the all level entrants and competitive exam at school level, provide notional level school educations, help to communication and personality development, bring the awareness about the higher education and women empowerment,

Conclusion

Challenges to women higher education in Thiruvallur District are divided into three categories (i) Social, (ii) Individual and (iii) Economic. Social and Individual challenges are changing in present but economic challenges belong to only economic bases. Role of government the school education literacy rate is very well, as it is, Government may come forward to raise women higher education literacy rate for welfare of women and Society.

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